

Optical properties of L-alanine passivated CdS nanoparticles

S. S. Talwatkar^a, A. L. Sunatkari^b, A. B. Gambhire^c, A. B. Naik^d, G. B. Harde^e and G. G. Muley^{*f}

^aDepartment of Physics, Acharya Marathe College, Chembur, Mumbai-400 071, India

^bDepartment of Physics, Siddharth College of ASC, Fort, Mumbai-400 023, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Anand College, Pathardi, Ahamednagar-414 102, Maharashtra, India

^dDepartment of Chemical Technology, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

^eDepartment of Physics, Shri R. R. Lahoti Science College, Morshi, Amravati-444 905, Maharashtra, India

^fDepartment of Physics, Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : gajananggm@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : CdS nanoparticles passivated with amino acid L-alanine having spherical hierarchical morphology were synthesized by low temperature wet chemical method. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy to know the variation of band gaps with concentration of surface modifying agents. Indeed, blue shift in band gap is observed and it increases with increasing concentration of surface modifying agents. Powder XRD, SEM and TEM analysis were carried out for the confirmation of formation of nanoparticles. Powder XRD study was done to confirm the crystal structure and Debye-Scherrer formula was used to find out the average particle size from the broadening of XRD peaks. The average particle size is found to less than 5 nm. FT-IR spectroscopy was performed to know the functional groups of the grown nanoparticles. From the observed peaks, it was confirmed that the CdS nanoparticles were capped by L-alanine. Photoluminescence study was performed on the grown CdS nanoparticles.

Keywords : Amino acid, CdS nanoparticles, powder XRD, photoluminescence, particle size.

Introduction

Nanoparticles show unique chemical, physical, optical, electrical and transport properties, which are very much different from those of both the bulk materials and single atoms. The nanoparticles poses huge surface area, due to that, the surface energy is very large, and it has to minimize in order to synthesize stable nanoparticles. This can be accomplished by capping nanoparticles with some capping agents. In the present study L-alanine was being used as a capping agent to synthesize CdS nanoparticles^{1,2}. CdS is wide band gap II-VI semiconductor of bulk band gap 2.42 eV. It exhibit size dependent properties like variation of band gap and melting point with size. As it is wide band gap semiconductor, it is used as visible light detector, window material for hetero junction solar cells and in other applications like in light emitting diodes, photo detectors, sensors and electrically driven lasers, etc.³⁻⁸.

L-Alanine is an α -amino acid with the chemical formula $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}$. The α -carbon atom of L-alanine is bound with a methyl group ($-\text{CH}_3$), making it one of the simplest α -amino acids with respect to molecular structure. The methyl group of L-alanine is non-reactive. The amino group has a lone pair of electron, zwitterionic structure and capable of forming hydrogen bonds^{9,10}. Due to its zwitterionic structure, it is expected that L-alanine can screen the field of nanoparticles and make them chemically stable.

In the present study, synthesis and characterization of CdS nanoparticles capped with L-alanine is being reported. The nanoparticles were synthesized by chemical precipitation method and characterized by UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, which gives evidence of blue shift in the band gap of CdS in confirmation of formation of nanoparticles with L-alanine as a capping agent. The shift in the position of peaks in Fourier transform infrared

(FT-IR) spectra of capped CdS nanoparticles reveals the formation of hydrogen bonding, which prevents an aggregation of particles and bulk crystal growth. XRD study confirms the nano size and cubical structure of CdS nanoparticles. SEM image also recorded. Photoluminescence study shows that the emission peaks around 554 nm and 588 nm.

Experimental

Materials and synthesis :

Cadmium chloride (CdCl_2), sodium sulphide (Na_2S), and L-alanine of AR grade were used for the synthesis of the samples. 1 M solutions of CdCl_2 and Na_2S were prepared separately by dissolving appropriate amount of solute in the 59.6 mL doubled distilled water. The solutions were stirred for long time, about 3 h, using magnetic stirrer and filtered using membrane filter papers. Same process was adopted to prepare 0.1 M 15 mL solution of L-alanine in doubled distilled water. 14.9 mL solution from prepared stock solution of CdCl_2 was taken in four beakers to prepare four samples; first sample (S0) for the preparation of CdS particles without any capping agent, second sample (S1) prepared by pouring 1.49 mL of 0.1 M L-alanine solution in the second beaker to prepare CdS nanoparticles with 1 mol% L-alanine capping agent and similarly the third (S2) and fourth (S3) samples were prepared by pouring 2.98 mL and 5.96 mL of 0.1 M L-alanine solution to prepare CdS nanoparticles with 2 mol% and 4 mol% L-alanine capping agent respectively. Doubled distilled water is added in all four beakers to make total volume 100 mL. Finally uncapped and capped CdS nanoparticles were synthesized by adding drop by drop 14.9 mL solution of Na_2S in each beaker with continuous vigorous stirring for 3 h. The transparent solution starts to become yellow with addition of Na_2S solution. The CdS nanoparticles without capping agent appear reddish orange in color and the color becomes dull with increasing concentration of L-alanine. The synthesized nanoparticles were then separated by centrifuging for 5 min with 4000 rpm. The nanoparticles were washed with water and ethanol followed by separation using centrifugation and dried optically to get powder. The synthesized nanoparticles were used for the further study.

The following chemical reaction takes place during synthesis of nanoparticles;

Characterizations :

UV-Vis spectroscopy of the grown nanoparticles was done using UV-1700 Shimadzu Spectrophotometer. The particle size was calculated using Debye-Scherrer formula and using powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) data obtained using PANalytical (Philips) X-ray diffractometer. The spherical hierarchical grown of particle was confirmed by SEM image of the particles, which was recorder on the instrument JEOL-JSM-6380 Scanning Electron Microscope (Japan). Particle size was confirmed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) also. Photoluminescence study was carried out using Hitachi Fluorescence Spectrophotometer F-7000.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectroscopy :

It is necessary to perform the UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy on the grown nanoparticles to know the absorption band. CdS is semiconductor with bulk band gap of 2.42 eV. The band gap increases with the decrease in particle size and shows blue shift effect from which the formation of nano size particles can be confirmed. The transmissions and absorptions of all the samples were measured over the wavelength range 200–1100 nm. The synthesized nanoparticles were dispersed in ethanol and were used for the characterizations. The UV-Vis spectra of all the samples are shown in the Fig. 1. The absorption curve shows that the absorption peak shifts toward shorter wavelength due to the increase in the band gap.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra.

Particle size and structural analysis :

The powder X-ray diffraction of L-alanine capped CdS nanoparticles were recorded in the 2θ range from $20\text{--}70^\circ$ and analysed using software PowderX. The peaks at diffraction angles $2\theta = 27.28, 30.81, 45.06$ and 52.19 degrees have been assigned to (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) crystallographic planes of the cubic structure of CdS respectively. The particle size of the synthesized nanoparticles was determined by using Debye-Scherrer's equation;

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

where, λ is the X-ray wavelength (1.54 \AA), k is the shape factor generally the value taken is 0.94, D is the average diameter of the crystals in Angstrom, θ is the Bragg angle in degree and β is the line broadening measured by half-height (Full width at half maxima) in radians.

The diffraction peaks associated with (1 1 1), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) crystallographic planes were chosen to calculate the size of the nanoparticles. The calculated particles sizes were found to 4.07, 3.78 and 3.43 nm for the samples S1, S2 and S3 respectively. The calculated values of the sizes of nanoparticles show that the size of the nanoparticles is less than 5 nm and decreases with increasing concentration of L-alanine.

Fig. 2(a) is a SEM image of synthesized nanoparticles showing spherical shape. Fig. 2(b) is TEM image showing nanoparticles of size less than 5 nm. Particle determined from XRD data are in good agreement with observed in TEM image.

Photoluminescence study :

The photoluminescence study was performed on the

Fig. 2. (a) SEM and (b) TEM images of sample S3.

Fig. 3. Emission spectra (Excitation at wavelength 230 nm).

prepared nanoparticles. The emission spectra (Fig. 3) of all the samples were taken using 230 nm as an excitation wavelength and emission was monitored over wavelength range 500–700 nm. The emission spectra show emission peaks centred at 554 nm and 588 nm for the sample S0. These emission peaks found to be shifted toward shorter wavelength by 3–4 nm for the samples S1–S3. Moreover it is observed that the intensity of peak at 554 nm is increased while the intensity of peak at 588 nm is decreased with increasing concentration of L-alanine. The green emission at around 520 nm and 554 nm is attributed to the emission due to electronic transition from the conduction band to an acceptor level due to interstitial sulphur¹⁴ and the yellow emission around 588 nm attributed to the recombination via surface localized states¹⁵ and a transition from interstitial cadmium to the valence band¹⁶.

Conclusions

CdS nanoparticles passivated with L-alanine were synthesized by chemical precipitation method. The UV-Vis spectroscopy confirms the blue shift in the band gap of CdS nanoparticles. XRD study shows that the nanoparticles have cubical structure and particle size < 5 nm which is also confirmed from TEM image also. In the emission spectra, it is found that the emission peaks are at around 554 nm and 588 nm. The intensity of peak at 588 nm decreases with concentration of L-alanine. Thus L-alanine is capable of screening the field of nanoparticles and prevents them from aggregation. CdS nanoparticles passivated with L-alanine can be used in many applications like, photo detectors, sensors, optical limiters, etc.

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